

Magic Squares of Order 25

The work is also available at author's site:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=9373>

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Abstract

*Recently, author [69] worked with **cornered** magic squares of order 6. Later this work is extended up to order 24 [69, 70, 71]. This work is for odd order magic squares. It for the order 25. In this work we have covered three types of magic squares. One **centered** magic squares. These are traditionally previously known magic squares. The second one is boarded with magic squares of order 5. The third one is **double digits bordered** magic squares. Some embedded examples are given where one type is embedded in another type. For previous works on odd orders from 3 to 23 refer [65, 66, 67]. Further studies of orders 27, 29 etc. shall be given in another works.*

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1 Introduction

Recently, author worked with **cornered magic squares** based on two-by-two digits:

1. Inder J. Taneja, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 13 [69, 70].
2. Inder J. Taneja, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 14 to 24 [71].

Also, the author worked on **even order double digits bordered** magic squares. This works starts from order 8 and goes up to order 40:

The work for order of type $4k, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ i.e., for orders 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, 32, 36 and 40:

1. Inder J. Taneja, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 4: Orders 8 to 24 [59].
2. Inder J. Taneja, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 28 and 32 [60].
3. Inder J. Taneja, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 36 and 40[63].

The work is for the order of type $4k + 2, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ i.e., for the orders 10, 14, 18, 22, 26, 30, 34 and 38:

1. Inder J. Taneja, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 10, 14, 18 and 22 [61].
2. Inder J. Taneja, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 26 and 30 [62].
3. Inder J. Taneja, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Order 34 and 38 [64].

2 Magic Squares of Order 25

In this work, we shall construct magic squares of order 25. It includes the following styles:

1. Centered magic squares.
2. Double digits bordered magic squares.
3. Bordered magic squares with borders of orders 5.
4. Cornered magic squares.

To construct **double digits** and **cornered** magic squares using software, the reader can follow H. Whites site [1]. Moreover, the **cornered** magic squares can be written in any of the four directions by using H. Whites [1] rotate program. Few examples can be seen at author's work [70, 71]. The previous work on odd orders from 3 to 23 refer author's work [65, 66, 67].

There are total 300 examples of magic squares of order 25. Below are only few examples. These are **centered** and **bordered** magic squares. It is of two types. One **boarded** with magic squares of order 5, and another as **double digits bordered** magic squares.

2.1 Centered Magic Squares

	pan	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825		
7825	1	220	284	498	562	417	606	75	139	328	183	272	461	530	119	599	38	227	316	385	365	429	518	82	171	7825	
7825	484	573	12	201	295	150	339	403	617	56	536	105	194	258	472	302	391	585	49	238	93	157	371	440	504	7825	
7825	212	276	495	559	23	603	67	131	350	414	269	458	547	111	180	35	249	313	377	591	446	515	79	168	357	7825	
7825	570	9	223	287	476	331	425	614	53	142	122	186	255	469	533	388	577	41	235	324	154	368	432	521	90	7825	
7825	298	487	551	20	209	64	128	342	406	625	455	544	108	197	261	241	310	399	588	27	507	96	165	354	443	7825	
7825	583	47	236	305	394	374	438	502	91	160	15	204	293	482	571	401	620	59	148	337	192	256	475	539	103	7825	
7825	311	380	594	33	247	77	166	360	449	513	493	557	21	215	279	134	348	412	601	70	550	114	178	267	456	7825	
7825	44	233	322	386	580	435	524	88	152	366	221	290	479	568	7	612	51	145	334	423	253	467	531	125	189	7825	
7825	397	586	30	244	308	163	352	441	510	99	554	18	207	296	490	345	409	623	62	126	106	200	264	453	542	7825	
7825	230	319	383	597	36	516	85	174	363	427	282	496	565	4	218	73	137	326	420	609	464	528	117	181	275	7825	
7825	415	604	68	132	346	176	270	459	548	112	592	31	250	314	378	358	447	511	80	169	24	213	277	491	560	7825	
7825	143	332	421	615	54	534	123	187	251	470	325	389	578	42	231	86	155	369	433	522	477	566	10	224	288	7825	
7825	621	65	129	343	407	262	451	545	109	198	28	242	306	400	589	444	508	97	161	355	210	299	488	552	16	7825	
7825	329	418	607	71	140	120	184	273	462	526	381	600	39	228	317	172	361	430	519	83	563	2	216	285	499	7825	
7825	57	146	340	404	618	473	537	101	195	259	239	303	392	581	50	505	94	158	372	436	291	485	574	13	202	7825	
7825	367	431	525	89	153	8	222	286	480	569	424	613	52	141	335	190	254	468	532	121	576	45	234	323	387	7825	
7825	100	164	353	442	506	486	555	19	208	297	127	341	410	624	63	543	107	196	265	454	309	398	587	26	245	7825	
7825	428	517	81	175	364	219	283	497	561	5	610	74	138	327	416	271	465	529	118	182	37	226	320	384	598	7825	
7825	156	375	439	503	92	572	11	205	294	483	338	402	616	60	149	104	193	257	471	540	395	584	48	237	301	7825	
7825	514	78	167	356	450	280	494	558	22	211	66	135	349	413	602	457	546	115	179	268	248	312	376	595	34	7825	
7825	199	263	452	541	110	590	29	243	307	396	351	445	509	98	162	17	206	300	489	553	408	622	61	130	344	7825	
7825	527	116	185	274	463	318	382	596	40	229	84	173	362	426	520	500	564	3	217	281	136	330	419	608	72	7825	
7825	260	474	538	102	191	46	240	304	393	582	437	501	95	159	373	203	292	481	575	14	619	58	147	336	405	7825	
7825	113	177	266	460	549	379	593	32	246	315	170	359	448	512	76	556	25	214	278	492	347	411	605	69	133	7825	
bi	466	535	124	188	252	232	321	390	579	43	523	87	151	370	434	289	478	567	6	225	55	144	333	422	611	7825	
1	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

It is **pandiagonal** and **bimagic** square order 25.

2	Inder J. Taneja																				https://inderjtaneja.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA					7825
602	578	580	582	584	586	588	590	592	594	596	598	23	22	20	18	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	600	7825											
47	556	534	536	538	540	542	544	546	548	550	552	69	68	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	50	554	579	7825											
45	91	514	494	496	498	500	502	504	506	508	510	111	110	108	106	104	102	100	98	96	94	512	535	581	7825											
43	89	131	476	458	460	462	464	466	468	470	472	149	148	146	144	142	140	138	136	134	474	495	537	583	7825											
41	87	129	167	442	426	428	430	432	434	436	438	183	182	180	178	176	174	172	170	440	459	497	539	585	7825											
39	85	127	165	199	412	398	400	402	404	406	408	213	212	210	208	206	204	202	410	427	461	499	541	587	7825											
37	83	125	163	197	227	386	374	376	378	380	382	239	238	236	234	232	230	384	399	429	463	501	543	589	7825											
35	81	123	161	195	225	251	364	354	356	358	360	261	260	258	256	254	362	375	401	431	465	503	545	591	7825											
33	79	121	159	193	223	249	271	346	338	340	342	279	278	276	274	344	355	377	403	433	467	505	547	593	7825											
31	77	119	157	191	221	247	269	287	332	326	328	293	292	290	330	339	357	379	405	435	469	507	549	595	7825											
29	75	117	155	189	219	245	267	285	299	322	318	303	302	320	327	341	359	381	407	437	471	509	551	597	7825											
27	73	115	153	187	217	243	265	283	297	307	316	309	314	319	329	343	361	383	409	439	473	511	553	599	7825											
25	71	113	151	185	215	241	263	281	295	305	311	313	315	321	331	345	363	385	411	441	475	513	555	601	7825											
605	559	517	479	445	415	389	367	349	335	325	312	317	310	301	291	277	259	237	211	181	147	109	67	21	7825											
607	561	519	481	447	417	391	369	351	337	306	308	323	324	304	289	275	257	235	209	179	145	107	65	19	7825											
609	563	521	483	449	419	393	371	353	296	300	298	333	334	336	294	273	255	233	207	177	143	105	63	17	7825											
611	565	523	485	451	421	395	373	282	288	286	284	347	348	350	352	280	253	231	205	175	141	103	61	15	7825											
613	567	525	487	453	423	397	264	272	270	268	266	365	366	368	370	372	262	229	203	173	139	101	59	13	7825											
615	569	527	489	455	425	242	252	250	248	246	244	387	388	390	392	394	396	240	201	171	137	99	57	11	7825											
617	571	529	491	457	216	228	226	224	222	220	218	413	414	416	418	420	422	424	214	169	135	97	55	9	7825											
619	573	531	493	186	200	198	196	194	192	190	188	443	444	446	448	450	452	454	456	184	133	95	53	7	7825											
621	575	533	152	168	166	164	162	160	158	156	154	477	478	480	482	484	486	488	490	492	150	93	51	5	7825											
623	577	114	132	130	128	126	124	122	120	118	116	515	516	518	520	522	524	526	528	530	532	112	49	3	7825											
625	72	92	90	88	86	84	82	80	78	76	74	557	558	560	562	564	566	568	570	572	574	576	70	1	7825											
26	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	32	30	28	603	604	606	608	610	612	614	616	618	620	622	624	24	7825											
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825										

3	Inder J. Taneja					https://inderjtaneja.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA					7825					
476	482	488	494	500	451	457	463	469	475	501	507	513	519	525	1	7	13	19	25	76	82	88	94	100	7825	
493	499	480	481	487	468	474	455	456	462	518	524	505	506	512	18	24	5	6	12	93	99	80	81	87	7825	
485	486	492	498	479	460	461	467	473	454	510	511	517	523	504	10	11	17	23	4	85	86	92	98	79	7825	
497	478	484	490	491	472	453	459	465	466	522	503	509	515	516	22	3	9	15	16	97	78	84	90	91	7825	
489	495	496	477	483	464	470	471	452	458	514	520	521	502	508	14	20	21	2	8	89	95	96	77	83	7825	
26	32	38	44	50	326	332	338	344	350	201	207	213	219	225	376	382	388	394	400	576	582	588	594	600	7825	
43	49	30	31	37	343	349	330	331	337	218	224	205	206	212	393	399	380	381	387	593	599	580	581	587	7825	
35	36	42	48	29	335	336	342	348	329	210	211	217	223	204	385	386	392	398	379	585	586	592	598	579	7825	
47	28	34	40	41	347	328	334	340	341	222	203	209	215	216	397	378	384	390	391	597	578	584	590	591	7825	
39	45	46	27	33	339	345	346	327	333	214	220	221	202	208	389	395	396	377	383	589	595	596	577	583	7825	
51	57	63	69	75	351	357	363	369	375	301	307	313	319	325	251	257	263	269	275	551	557	563	569	575	7825	
68	74	55	56	62	368	374	355	356	362	318	324	305	306	312	268	274	255	256	262	568	574	555	556	562	7825	
60	61	67	73	54	360	361	367	373	354	310	311	317	323	304	260	261	267	273	254	560	561	567	573	554	7825	
72	53	59	65	66	372	353	359	365	366	322	303	309	315	316	272	253	259	265	266	572	553	559	565	566	7825	
64	70	71	52	58	364	370	371	352	358	314	320	321	302	308	264	270	271	252	258	564	570	571	552	558	7825	
426	432	438	444	450	226	232	238	244	250	401	407	413	419	425	276	282	288	294	300	176	182	188	194	200	7825	
443	449	430	431	437	243	249	230	231	237	418	424	405	406	412	293	299	280	281	287	193	199	180	181	187	7825	
435	436	442	448	429	235	236	242	248	229	410	411	417	423	404	285	286	292	298	279	185	186	192	198	179	7825	
447	428	434	440	441	247	228	234	240	241	422	403	409	415	416	297	278	284	290	291	197	178	184	190	191	7825	
439	445	446	427	433	239	245	246	227	233	414	420	421	402	408	289	295	296	277	283	189	195	196	177	183	7825	
526	532	538	544	550	151	157	163	169	175	101	107	113	119	125	601	607	613	619	625	126	132	138	144	150	7825	
543	549	530	531	537	168	174	155	156	162	118	124	105	106	112	618	624	605	606	612	143	149	130	131	137	7825	
535	536	542	548	529	160	161	167	173	154	110	111	117	123	104	610	611	617	623	604	135	136	142	148	129	7825	
547	528	534	540	541	172	153	159	165	166	122	103	109	115	116	622	603	609	615	616	147	128	134	140	141	7825	
539	545	546	527	533	164	170	171	152	158	114	120	121	102	108	614	620	621	602	608	139	145	146	127	133	7825	
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

4	Inder J. Taneja	https://inderjtaneja.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	7825																				
497	500	480	482	481	472	475	455	457	456	522	525	505	507	506	22	25	5	7	6	97	100	80	82	81	7825
477	487	492	485	499	452	462	467	460	474	502	512	517	510	524	2	12	17	10	24	77	87	92	85	99	7825
478	486	488	490	498	453	461	463	465	473	503	511	513	515	523	3	11	13	15	23	78	86	88	90	98	7825
493	491	484	489	483	468	466	459	464	458	518	516	509	514	508	18	16	9	14	8	93	91	84	89	83	7825
495	476	496	494	479	470	451	471	469	454	520	501	521	519	504	20	1	21	19	4	95	76	96	94	79	7825
47	50	30	32	31	347	350	330	332	331	222	225	205	207	206	397	400	380	382	381	597	600	580	582	581	7825
27	37	42	35	49	327	337	342	335	349	202	212	217	210	224	377	387	392	385	399	577	587	592	585	599	7825
28	36	38	40	48	328	336	338	340	348	203	211	213	215	223	378	386	388	390	398	578	586	588	590	598	7825
43	41	34	39	33	343	341	334	339	333	218	216	209	214	208	393	391	384	389	383	593	591	584	589	583	7825
45	26	46	44	29	345	326	346	344	329	220	201	221	219	204	395	376	396	394	379	595	576	596	594	579	7825
72	75	55	57	56	372	375	355	357	356	322	325	305	307	306	272	275	255	257	256	572	575	555	557	556	7825
52	62	67	60	74	352	362	367	360	374	302	312	317	310	324	252	262	267	260	274	552	562	567	560	574	7825
53	61	63	65	73	353	361	363	365	373	303	311	313	315	323	253	261	263	265	273	553	561	563	565	573	7825
68	66	59	64	58	368	366	359	364	358	318	316	309	314	308	268	266	259	264	258	568	566	559	564	558	7825
70	51	71	69	54	370	351	371	369	354	320	301	321	319	304	270	251	271	269	254	570	551	571	569	554	7825
447	450	430	432	431	247	250	230	232	231	422	425	405	407	406	297	300	280	282	281	197	200	180	182	181	7825
427	437	442	435	449	227	237	242	235	249	402	412	417	410	424	277	287	292	285	299	177	187	192	185	199	7825
428	436	438	440	448	228	236	238	240	248	403	411	413	415	423	278	286	288	290	298	178	186	188	190	198	7825
443	441	434	439	433	243	241	234	239	233	418	416	409	414	408	293	291	284	289	283	193	191	184	189	183	7825
445	426	446	444	429	245	226	246	244	229	420	401	421	419	404	295	276	296	294	279	195	176	196	194	179	7825
547	550	530	532	531	172	175	155	157	156	122	125	105	107	106	622	625	605	607	606	147	150	130	132	131	7825
527	537	542	535	549	152	162	167	160	174	102	112	117	110	124	602	612	617	610	624	127	137	142	135	149	7825
528	536	538	540	548	153	161	163	165	173	103	111	113	115	123	603	611	613	615	623	128	136	138	140	148	7825
543	541	534	539	533	168	166	159	164	158	118	116	109	114	108	618	616	609	614	608	143	141	134	139	133	7825
545	526	546	544	529	170	151	171	169	154	120	101	121	119	104	620	601	621	619	604	145	126	146	144	129	7825
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

2.2 Part 1: Bordered With Magic Squares of Order 5

5	Inder J. Taneja					https://inderjtaneja.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA					7825				
476	482	488	494	500	451	457	463	469	475	501	507	513	519	525	1	7	13	19	25	76	82	88	94	100	7825
493	499	480	481	487	468	474	455	456	462	518	524	505	506	512	18	24	5	6	12	93	99	80	81	87	7825
485	486	492	498	479	460	461	467	473	454	510	511	517	523	504	10	11	17	23	4	85	86	92	98	79	7825
497	478	484	490	491	472	453	459	465	466	522	503	509	515	516	22	3	9	15	16	97	78	84	90	91	7825
489	495	496	477	483	464	470	471	452	458	514	520	521	502	508	14	20	21	2	8	89	95	96	77	83	7825
26	32	38	44	50	386	265	288	387	274	278	388	275	276	389	264	286	390	262	287	576	582	588	594	600	7825
43	49	30	31	37	280	393	266	289	383	267	290	381	268	279	391	269	277	392	270	593	599	580	581	587	7825
35	36	42	48	29	273	281	385	263	282	394	261	283	395	271	284	384	272	285	382	585	586	592	598	579	7825
47	28	34	40	41	236	400	303	237	409	293	238	410	291	239	399	301	240	397	302	597	578	584	590	591	7825
39	45	46	27	33	295	243	401	304	233	402	305	231	403	294	241	404	292	242	405	589	595	596	577	583	7825
51	57	63	69	75	408	296	235	398	297	244	396	298	245	406	299	234	407	300	232	551	557	563	569	575	7825
68	74	55	56	62	206	415	318	207	424	308	208	425	306	209	414	316	210	412	317	568	574	555	556	562	7825
60	61	67	73	54	310	213	416	319	203	417	320	201	418	309	211	419	307	212	420	560	561	567	573	554	7825
72	53	59	65	66	423	311	205	413	312	214	411	313	215	421	314	204	422	315	202	572	553	559	565	566	7825
64	70	71	52	58	356	250	333	357	259	323	358	260	321	359	249	331	360	247	332	564	570	571	552	558	7825
426	432	438	444	450	325	363	251	334	353	252	335	351	253	324	361	254	322	362	255	176	182	188	194	200	7825
443	449	430	431	437	258	326	355	248	327	364	246	328	365	256	329	354	257	330	352	193	199	180	181	187	7825
435	436	442	448	429	371	220	348	372	229	338	373	230	336	374	219	346	375	217	347	185	186	192	198	179	7825
447	428	434	440	441	340	378	221	349	368	222	350	366	223	339	376	224	337	377	225	197	178	184	190	191	7825
439	445	446	427	433	228	341	370	218	342	379	216	343	380	226	344	369	227	345	367	189	195	196	177	183	7825
526	532	538	544	550	151	157	163	169	175	101	107	113	119	125	601	607	613	619	625	126	132	138	144	150	7825
543	549	530	531	537	168	174	155	156	162	118	124	105	106	112	618	624	605	606	612	143	149	130	131	137	7825
535	536	542	548	529	160	161	167	173	154	110	111	117	123	104	610	611	617	623	604	135	136	142	148	129	7825
547	528	534	540	541	172	153	159	165	166	122	103	109	115	116	622	603	609	615	616	147	128	134	140	141	7825
539	545	546	527	533	164	170	171	152	158	114	120	121	102	108	614	620	621	602	608	139	145	146	127	133	7825
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

6	Inder J. Taneja					https://inderjtaneja.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA					7825					
476	482	488	494	500	451	457	463	469	475	501	507	513	519	525	1	7	13	19	25	76	82	88	94	100	7825	
493	499	480	481	487	468	474	455	456	462	518	524	505	506	512	18	24	5	6	12	93	99	80	81	87	7825	
485	486	492	498	479	460	461	467	473	454	510	511	517	523	504	10	11	17	23	4	85	86	92	98	79	7825	
497	478	484	490	491	472	453	459	465	466	522	503	509	515	516	22	3	9	15	16	97	78	84	90	91	7825	
489	495	496	477	483	464	470	471	452	458	514	520	521	502	508	14	20	21	2	8	89	95	96	77	83	7825	
26	32	38	44	50	297	300	280	282	281	422	425	405	407	406	247	250	230	232	231	576	582	588	594	600	7825	
43	49	30	31	37	277	287	292	285	299	402	412	417	410	424	227	237	242	235	249	593	599	580	581	587	7825	
35	36	42	48	29	278	286	288	290	298	403	411	413	415	423	228	236	238	240	248	585	586	592	598	579	7825	
47	28	34	40	41	293	291	284	289	283	418	416	409	414	408	243	241	234	239	233	597	578	584	590	591	7825	
39	45	46	27	33	295	276	296	294	279	420	401	421	419	404	245	226	246	244	229	589	595	596	577	583	7825	
51	57	63	69	75	272	275	255	257	256	322	325	305	307	306	372	375	355	357	356	551	557	563	569	575	7825	
68	74	55	56	62	252	262	267	260	274	302	312	317	310	324	352	362	367	360	374	568	574	555	556	562	7825	
60	61	67	73	54	253	261	263	265	273	303	311	313	315	323	353	361	363	365	373	560	561	567	573	554	7825	
72	53	59	65	66	268	266	259	264	258	318	316	309	314	308	368	366	359	364	358	572	553	559	565	566	7825	
64	70	71	52	58	270	251	271	269	254	320	301	321	319	304	370	351	371	369	354	564	570	571	552	558	7825	
426	432	438	444	450	397	400	380	382	381	222	225	205	207	206	347	350	330	332	331	176	182	188	194	200	7825	
443	449	430	431	437	377	387	392	385	399	202	212	217	210	224	327	337	342	335	349	193	199	180	181	187	7825	
435	436	442	448	429	378	386	388	390	398	203	211	213	215	223	328	336	338	340	348	185	186	192	198	179	7825	
447	428	434	440	441	393	391	384	389	383	218	216	209	214	208	343	341	334	339	333	197	178	184	190	191	7825	
439	445	446	427	433	395	376	396	394	379	220	201	221	219	204	345	326	346	344	329	189	195	196	177	183	7825	
526	532	538	544	550	151	157	163	169	175	101	107	113	119	125	601	607	613	619	625	126	132	138	144	150	7825	
543	549	530	531	537	168	174	155	156	162	118	124	105	106	112	618	624	605	606	612	143	149	130	131	137	7825	
535	536	542	548	529	160	161	167	173	154	110	111	117	123	104	610	611	617	623	604	135	136	142	148	129	7825	
547	528	534	540	541	172	153	159	165	166	122	103	109	115	116	622	603	609	615	616	147	128	134	140	141	7825	
539	545	546	527	533	164	170	171	152	158	114	120	121	102	108	614	620	621	602	608	139	145	146	127	133	7825	
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

15	Inder J. Taneja					https://inderjtaneja.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA					7825					
476	482	488	494	500	451	457	463	469	475	501	507	513	519	525	1	7	13	19	25	76	82	88	94	100	7825	
493	499	480	481	487	468	474	455	456	462	518	524	505	506	512	18	24	5	6	12	93	99	80	81	87	7825	
485	486	492	498	479	460	461	467	473	454	510	511	517	523	504	10	11	17	23	4	85	86	92	98	79	7825	
497	478	484	490	491	472	453	459	465	466	522	503	509	515	516	22	3	9	15	16	97	78	84	90	91	7825	
489	495	496	477	483	464	470	471	452	458	514	520	521	502	508	14	20	21	2	8	89	95	96	77	83	7825	
26	32	38	44	50	405	412	249	246	400	396	388	236	232	207	250	413	235	234	392	576	582	588	594	600	7825	
43	49	30	31	37	221	214	377	380	226	230	238	390	394	419	376	213	391	244	382	593	599	580	581	587	7825	
35	36	42	48	29	401	225	301	307	313	319	325	326	300	279	347	271	355	420	206	585	586	592	598	579	7825	
47	28	34	40	41	416	210	318	324	305	306	312	333	293	288	338	362	264	245	381	597	578	584	590	591	7825	
39	45	46	27	33	211	415	310	311	317	323	304	330	296	284	342	265	361	248	378	589	595	596	577	583	7825	
51	57	63	69	75	241	385	322	303	309	315	316	327	299	286	340	372	254	223	403	551	557	563	569	575	7825	
68	74	55	56	62	393	233	314	320	321	302	308	291	335	349	277	267	359	375	251	568	574	555	556	562	7825	
60	61	67	73	54	397	229	328	292	329	332	290	289	331	346	280	263	363	408	218	560	561	567	573	554	7825	
72	53	59	65	66	217	409	298	334	297	294	336	295	337	285	341	367	259	422	204	572	553	559	565	566	7825	
64	70	71	52	58	203	423	350	351	287	281	282	283	353	352	278	368	258	201	425	564	570	571	552	558	7825	
426	432	438	444	450	208	418	276	275	339	345	344	343	273	348	274	272	354	411	215	176	182	188	194	200	7825	
443	449	430	431	437	395	231	364	256	358	255	253	357	261	360	257	366	356	228	398	193	199	180	181	187	7825	
435	436	442	448	429	219	407	262	370	268	371	373	269	365	266	369	270	260	410	216	185	186	192	198	179	7825	
447	428	434	440	441	389	237	252	399	239	220	414	243	386	242	205	404	224	424	417	197	178	184	190	191	7825	
439	445	446	427	433	379	247	374	227	387	406	212	383	240	384	421	222	402	202	209	189	195	196	177	183	7825	
526	532	538	544	550	151	157	163	169	175	101	107	113	119	125	601	607	613	619	625	126	132	138	144	150	7825	
543	549	530	531	537	168	174	155	156	162	118	124	105	106	112	618	624	605	606	612	143	149	130	131	137	7825	
535	536	542	548	529	160	161	167	173	154	110	111	117	123	104	610	611	617	623	604	135	136	142	148	129	7825	
547	528	534	540	541	172	153	159	165	166	122	103	109	115	116	622	603	609	615	616	147	128	134	140	141	7825	
539	545	546	527	533	164	170	171	152	158	114	120	121	102	108	614	620	621	602	608	139	145	146	127	133	7825	
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

Above there are only three examples. Complete work as **pdf file** can be download from author's site [2].

2.3 Part 2: Bordered With Bordered Magic Squares of Order 5

45	Inder J. Taneja					https://inderjtaneja.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA					7825				
497	500	480	482	481	472	475	455	457	456	522	525	505	507	506	22	25	5	7	6	97	100	80	82	81	7825
477	487	492	485	499	452	462	467	460	474	502	512	517	510	524	2	12	17	10	24	77	87	92	85	99	7825
478	486	488	490	498	453	461	463	465	473	503	511	513	515	523	3	11	13	15	23	78	86	88	90	98	7825
493	491	484	489	483	468	466	459	464	458	518	516	509	514	508	18	16	9	14	8	93	91	84	89	83	7825
495	476	496	494	479	470	451	471	469	454	520	501	521	519	504	20	1	21	19	4	95	76	96	94	79	7825
47	50	30	32	31	386	265	288	387	274	278	388	275	276	389	264	286	390	262	287	597	600	580	582	581	7825
27	37	42	35	49	280	393	266	289	383	267	290	381	268	279	391	269	277	392	270	577	587	592	585	599	7825
28	36	38	40	48	273	281	385	263	282	394	261	283	395	271	284	384	272	285	382	578	586	588	590	598	7825
43	41	34	39	33	236	400	303	237	409	293	238	410	291	239	399	301	240	397	302	593	591	584	589	583	7825
45	26	46	44	29	295	243	401	304	233	402	305	231	403	294	241	404	292	242	405	595	576	596	594	579	7825
72	75	55	57	56	408	296	235	398	297	244	396	298	245	406	299	234	407	300	232	572	575	555	557	556	7825
52	62	67	60	74	206	415	318	207	424	308	208	425	306	209	414	316	210	412	317	552	562	567	560	574	7825
53	61	63	65	73	310	213	416	319	203	417	320	201	418	309	211	419	307	212	420	553	561	563	565	573	7825
68	66	59	64	58	423	311	205	413	312	214	411	313	215	421	314	204	422	315	202	568	566	559	564	558	7825
70	51	71	69	54	356	250	333	357	259	323	358	260	321	359	249	331	360	247	332	570	551	571	569	554	7825
447	450	430	432	431	325	363	251	334	353	252	335	351	253	324	361	254	322	362	255	197	200	180	182	181	7825
427	437	442	435	449	258	326	355	248	327	364	246	328	365	256	329	354	257	330	352	177	187	192	185	199	7825
428	436	438	440	448	371	220	348	372	229	338	373	230	336	374	219	346	375	217	347	178	186	188	190	198	7825
443	441	434	439	433	340	378	221	349	368	222	350	366	223	339	376	224	337	377	225	193	191	184	189	183	7825
445	426	446	444	429	228	341	370	218	342	379	216	343	380	226	344	369	227	345	367	195	176	196	194	179	7825
547	550	530	532	531	172	175	155	157	156	122	125	105	107	106	622	625	605	607	606	147	150	130	132	131	7825
527	537	542	535	549	152	162	167	160	174	102	112	117	110	124	602	612	617	610	624	127	137	142	135	149	7825
528	536	538	540	548	153	161	163	165	173	103	111	113	115	123	603	611	613	615	623	128	136	138	140	148	7825
543	541	534	539	533	168	166	159	164	158	118	116	109	114	108	618	616	609	614	608	143	141	134	139	133	7825
545	526	546	544	529	170	151	171	169	154	120	101	121	119	104	620	601	621	619	604	145	126	146	144	129	7825
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

46	Inder J. Taneja					https://inderjtaneja.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA					7825				
497	500	480	482	481	472	475	455	457	456	522	525	505	507	506	22	25	5	7	6	97	100	80	82	81	7825
477	487	492	485	499	452	462	467	460	474	502	512	517	510	524	2	12	17	10	24	77	87	92	85	99	7825
478	486	488	490	498	453	461	463	465	473	503	511	513	515	523	3	11	13	15	23	78	86	88	90	98	7825
493	491	484	489	483	468	466	459	464	458	518	516	509	514	508	18	16	9	14	8	93	91	84	89	83	7825
495	476	496	494	479	470	451	471	469	454	520	501	521	519	504	20	1	21	19	4	95	76	96	94	79	7825
47	50	30	32	31	410	399	401	403	405	407	409	411	211	209	207	205	203	201	214	597	600	580	582	581	7825
27	37	42	35	49	202	384	375	377	379	381	383	385	237	235	233	231	229	240	424	577	587	592	585	599	7825
28	36	38	40	48	204	230	264	272	270	268	266	365	366	368	370	372	262	396	422	578	586	588	590	598	7825
43	41	34	39	33	206	232	373	280	352	350	348	347	284	286	288	282	253	394	420	593	591	584	589	583	7825
45	26	46	44	29	208	234	371	273	330	326	328	293	292	290	332	353	255	392	418	595	576	596	594	579	7825
72	75	55	57	56	210	236	369	275	289	322	325	305	307	306	337	351	257	390	416	572	575	555	557	556	7825
52	62	67	60	74	212	238	367	277	291	302	312	317	310	324	335	349	259	388	414	552	562	567	560	574	7825
53	61	63	65	73	213	239	263	345	331	303	311	313	315	323	295	281	363	387	413	553	561	563	565	573	7825
68	66	59	64	58	408	382	265	343	329	318	316	309	314	308	297	283	361	244	218	568	566	559	564	558	7825
70	51	71	69	54	406	380	267	341	327	320	301	321	319	304	299	285	359	246	220	570	551	571	569	554	7825
447	450	430	432	431	404	378	269	339	294	300	298	333	334	336	296	287	357	248	222	197	200	180	182	181	7825
427	437	442	435	449	402	376	271	344	274	276	278	279	342	340	338	346	355	250	224	177	187	192	185	199	7825
428	436	438	440	448	400	374	364	354	356	358	360	261	260	258	256	254	362	252	226	178	186	188	190	198	7825
443	441	434	439	433	398	386	251	249	247	245	243	241	389	391	393	395	397	242	228	193	191	184	189	183	7825
445	426	446	444	429	412	227	225	223	221	219	217	215	415	417	419	421	423	425	216	195	176	196	194	179	7825
547	550	530	532	531	172	175	155	157	156	122	125	105	107	106	622	625	605	607	606	147	150	130	132	131	7825
527	537	542	535	549	152	162	167	160	174	102	112	117	110	124	602	612	617	610	624	127	137	142	135	149	7825
528	536	538	540	548	153	161	163	165	173	103	111	113	115	123	603	611	613	615	623	128	136	138	140	148	7825
543	541	534	539	533	168	166	159	164	158	118	116	109	114	108	618	616	609	614	608	143	141	134	139	133	7825
545	526	546	544	529	170	151	171	169	154	120	101	121	119	104	620	601	621	619	604	145	126	146	144	129	7825
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

60	Inder J. Taneja					https://inderjtaneja.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA					7825				
497	500	480	482	481	472	475	455	457	456	522	525	505	507	506	22	25	5	7	6	97	100	80	82	81	7825
477	487	492	485	499	452	462	467	460	474	502	512	517	510	524	2	12	17	10	24	77	87	92	85	99	7825
478	486	488	490	498	453	461	463	465	473	503	511	513	515	523	3	11	13	15	23	78	86	88	90	98	7825
493	491	484	489	483	468	466	459	464	458	518	516	509	514	508	18	16	9	14	8	93	91	84	89	83	7825
495	476	496	494	479	470	451	471	469	454	520	501	521	519	504	20	1	21	19	4	95	76	96	94	79	7825
47	50	30	32	31	310	317	312	325	301	327	299	344	282	267	359	252	374	209	417	597	600	580	582	581	7825
27	37	42	35	49	315	313	311	324	302	333	293	342	284	264	362	241	385	203	423	577	587	592	585	599	7825
28	36	38	40	48	314	309	316	304	322	294	332	279	347	367	259	240	386	208	418	578	586	588	590	598	7825
43	41	34	39	33	308	306	323	307	321	289	337	278	348	368	258	384	242	405	221	593	591	584	589	583	7825
45	26	46	44	29	318	320	303	305	319	292	334	340	286	263	363	250	376	207	419	595	576	596	594	579	7825
72	75	55	57	56	290	291	331	328	329	326	296	338	288	262	364	391	235	401	225	572	575	555	557	556	7825
52	62	67	60	74	336	335	295	298	297	330	300	346	280	371	255	395	231	413	213	552	562	567	560	574	7825
53	61	63	65	73	349	353	287	283	281	351	285	276	352	372	254	390	236	406	220	553	561	563	565	573	7825
68	66	59	64	58	277	273	339	343	345	275	341	274	350	271	355	245	381	201	425	568	566	559	564	558	7825
70	51	71	69	54	270	260	269	370	365	272	369	266	268	373	361	251	375	403	223	570	551	571	569	554	7825
447	450	430	432	431	356	366	357	256	261	354	257	360	358	265	253	396	230	206	420	197	200	180	182	181	7825
427	437	442	435	449	380	234	382	383	379	232	387	233	377	238	378	237	229	415	211	177	187	192	185	199	7825
428	436	438	440	448	246	392	244	243	247	394	239	393	249	388	248	397	389	210	416	178	186	188	190	198	7825
443	441	434	439	433	424	421	411	226	217	412	219	224	414	422	222	218	227	410	228	193	191	184	189	183	7825
445	426	446	444	429	202	205	215	400	409	214	407	402	212	204	404	408	399	398	216	195	176	196	194	179	7825
547	550	530	532	531	172	175	155	157	156	122	125	105	107	106	622	625	605	607	606	147	150	130	132	131	7825
527	537	542	535	549	152	162	167	160	174	102	112	117	110	124	602	612	617	610	624	127	137	142	135	149	7825
528	536	538	540	548	153	161	163	165	173	103	111	113	115	123	603	611	613	615	623	128	136	138	140	148	7825
543	541	534	539	533	168	166	159	164	158	118	116	109	114	108	618	616	609	614	608	143	141	134	139	133	7825
545	526	546	544	529	170	151	171	169	154	120	101	121	119	104	620	601	621	619	604	145	126	146	144	129	7825
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

Above there are only three examples. Complete work as **pdf file** can be download from author's site [2].

2.4 Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares

91	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA					7825								
8	9	548	57	602	68	4	595	36	47	72	551	534	559	35	66	550	570	5	540	606	601	536	581	45	7825	
618	617	78	569	24	558	622	31	590	579	554	75	92	67	591	560	76	56	621	86	20	25	90	14	612	7825	
552	74	483	488	481	429	434	427	447	452	445	132	137	130	123	128	121	105	110	103	465	470	463	544	82	7825	
80	546	482	484	486	428	430	432	446	448	450	131	133	135	122	124	126	104	106	108	464	466	468	616	10	7825	
557	69	487	480	485	433	426	431	451	444	449	136	129	134	127	120	125	109	102	107	469	462	467	580	46	7825	
54	572	186	191	184	405	412	249	246	400	396	388	236	232	207	250	413	235	234	392	438	443	436	556	70	7825	
567	59	185	187	189	221	214	377	380	226	230	238	390	394	419	376	213	391	244	382	437	439	441	561	65	7825	
19	607	190	183	188	401	225	262	285	368	266	280	362	359	363	272	269	357	420	206	442	435	440	585	41	7825	
81	545	168	173	166	416	210	364	341	258	360	346	264	267	263	354	353	273	245	381	456	461	454	60	566	7825	
547	79	167	169	171	211	415	352	274	321	298	308	301	337	320	306	344	282	248	378	455	457	459	568	58	7825	
594	32	172	165	170	241	385	369	257	305	328	318	325	289	293	333	270	356	223	403	460	453	458	564	62	7825	
84	542	150	155	148	393	233	279	347	302	324	316	309	314	290	336	370	256	375	251	474	479	472	3	623	7825	
27	599	149	151	153	397	229	259	367	327	299	311	313	315	330	296	350	276	408	218	473	475	477	541	85	7825	
538	88	154	147	152	217	409	268	358	295	331	312	317	310	332	294	253	373	422	204	478	471	476	16	610	7825	
21	605	510	515	508	203	423	343	283	307	319	291	322	329	300	323	260	366	201	425	114	119	112	38	588	7825	
23	603	509	511	513	208	418	287	339	334	292	335	304	297	326	303	348	278	411	215	113	115	117	17	609	7825	
577	49	514	507	512	395	231	372	254	371	277	286	275	355	281	265	365	342	228	398	118	111	116	13	613	7825	
1	625	528	533	526	219	407	288	338	255	349	340	351	271	345	361	261	284	410	216	96	101	94	18	608	7825	
549	77	527	529	531	389	237	252	399	239	220	414	243	386	242	205	404	224	424	417	95	97	99	34	592	7825	
537	89	532	525	530	379	247	374	227	387	406	212	383	240	384	421	222	402	202	209	100	93	98	50	576	7825	
604	22	159	164	157	195	200	193	177	182	175	492	497	490	501	506	499	519	524	517	141	146	139	615	11	7825	
553	73	158	160	162	194	196	198	176	178	180	491	493	495	500	502	504	518	520	522	140	142	144	29	597	7825	
15	611	163	156	161	199	192	197	181	174	179	496	489	494	505	498	503	523	516	521	145	138	143	596	30	7825	
26	600	48	598	6	555	563	61	614	562	44	43	42	53	2	37	535	7	539	40	571	543	587	575	574	7825	
593	33	578	28	620	71	63	565	12	64	582	583	584	573	624	589	91	619	87	586	55	83	39	51	52	7825	
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

104		Inder J. Taneja					https://inderjtaneja.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA					7825				
8	9	548	57	602	68	4	595	36	47	72	551	534	559	35	66	550	570	5	540	606	601	536	581	45	7825	
618	617	78	569	24	558	622	31	590	579	554	75	92	67	591	560	76	56	621	86	20	25	90	14	612	7825	
552	74	483	488	481	429	434	427	447	452	445	132	137	130	123	128	121	105	110	103	465	470	463	544	82	7825	
80	546	482	484	486	428	430	432	446	448	450	131	133	135	122	124	126	104	106	108	464	466	468	616	10	7825	
557	69	487	480	485	433	426	431	451	444	449	136	129	134	127	120	125	109	102	107	469	462	467	580	46	7825	
54	572	186	191	184	310	317	312	325	301	327	299	344	282	267	359	252	374	209	417	438	443	436	556	70	7825	
567	59	185	187	189	315	313	311	324	302	333	293	342	284	264	362	241	385	203	423	437	439	441	561	65	7825	
19	607	190	183	188	314	309	316	304	322	294	332	279	347	367	259	240	386	208	418	442	435	440	585	41	7825	
81	545	168	173	166	308	306	323	307	321	289	337	278	348	368	258	384	242	405	221	456	461	454	60	566	7825	
547	79	167	169	171	318	320	303	305	319	292	334	340	286	263	363	250	376	207	419	455	457	459	568	58	7825	
594	32	172	165	170	290	291	331	328	329	326	296	338	288	262	364	391	235	401	225	460	453	458	564	62	7825	
84	542	150	155	148	336	335	295	298	297	330	300	346	280	371	255	395	231	413	213	474	479	472	3	623	7825	
27	599	149	151	153	349	353	287	283	281	351	285	276	352	372	254	390	236	406	220	473	475	477	541	85	7825	
538	88	154	147	152	277	273	339	343	345	275	341	274	350	271	355	245	381	201	425	478	471	476	16	610	7825	
21	605	510	515	508	270	260	269	370	365	272	369	266	268	373	361	251	375	403	223	114	119	112	38	588	7825	
23	603	509	511	513	356	366	357	256	261	354	257	360	358	265	253	396	230	206	420	113	115	117	17	609	7825	
577	49	514	507	512	380	234	382	383	379	232	387	233	377	238	378	237	229	415	211	118	111	116	13	613	7825	
1	625	528	533	526	246	392	244	243	247	394	239	393	249	388	248	397	389	210	416	96	101	94	18	608	7825	
549	77	527	529	531	424	421	411	226	217	412	219	224	414	422	222	218	227	410	228	95	97	99	34	592	7825	
537	89	532	525	530	202	205	215	400	409	214	407	402	212	204	404	408	399	398	216	100	93	98	50	576	7825	
604	22	159	164	157	195	200	193	177	182	175	492	497	490	501	506	499	519	524	517	141	146	139	615	11	7825	
553	73	158	160	162	194	196	198	176	178	180	491	493	495	500	502	504	518	520	522	140	142	144	29	597	7825	
15	611	163	156	161	199	192	197	181	174	179	496	489	494	505	498	503	523	516	521	145	138	143	596	30	7825	
26	600	48	598	6	555	563	61	614	562	44	43	42	53	2	37	535	7	539	40	571	543	587	575	574	7825	
593	33	578	28	620	71	63	565	12	64	582	583	584	573	624	589	91	619	87	586	55	83	39	51	52	7825	
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

136		Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/		https://numbers-magic.com/		@IJTANEJA		7825																
8	9	548	57	602	68	4	595	36	47	72	551	534	559	35	66	550	570	5	540	606	601	536	581	45	7825	
618	617	78	569	24	558	622	31	590	579	554	75	92	67	591	560	76	56	621	86	20	25	90	14	612	7825	
552	74	462	513	479	464	467	110	150	105	494	493	141	107	130	470	120	165	465	121	491	115	511	544	82	7825	
80	546	164	113	147	162	159	516	476	521	132	133	485	519	496	156	506	461	161	505	135	126	500	616	10	7825	
557	69	515	111	184	456	454	452	450	448	446	444	443	188	190	192	194	196	198	200	186	486	140	580	46	7825	
54	572	514	112	169	410	399	401	403	405	407	409	411	211	209	207	205	203	201	214	457	472	154	556	70	7825	
567	59	145	481	171	202	384	375	377	379	381	383	385	237	235	233	231	229	240	424	455	459	167	561	65	7825	
19	607	523	103	173	204	230	264	272	270	268	266	365	366	368	370	372	262	396	422	453	146	480	585	41	7825	
81	545	149	477	175	206	232	373	280	352	350	348	347	284	286	288	282	253	394	420	451	131	495	60	566	7825	
547	79	157	469	177	208	234	371	273	296	300	298	333	334	336	294	353	255	392	418	449	522	104	568	58	7825	
594	32	129	497	179	210	236	369	275	337	304	301	321	319	320	289	351	257	390	416	447	498	128	564	62	7825	
84	542	143	483	181	212	238	367	277	335	324	314	309	316	302	291	349	259	388	414	445	124	502	3	623	7825	
27	599	117	509	441	213	239	263	345	295	323	315	313	311	303	331	281	363	387	413	185	102	524	541	85	7825	
538	88	466	160	439	408	382	265	343	297	308	310	317	312	318	329	283	361	244	218	187	100	526	16	610	7825	
21	605	122	504	437	406	380	267	341	299	306	325	305	307	322	327	285	359	246	220	189	152	474	38	588	7825	
23	603	492	134	435	404	378	269	339	332	326	328	293	292	290	330	287	357	248	222	191	463	163	17	609	7825	
577	49	151	475	433	402	376	271	344	274	276	278	279	342	340	338	346	355	250	224	193	99	527	13	613	7825	
1	625	530	96	431	400	374	364	354	356	358	360	261	260	258	256	254	362	252	226	195	510	116	18	608	7825	
549	77	119	507	429	398	386	251	249	247	245	243	241	389	391	393	395	397	242	228	197	484	142	34	592	7825	
537	89	138	488	427	412	227	225	223	221	219	217	215	415	417	419	421	423	425	216	199	487	139	50	576	7825	
604	22	490	136	440	170	172	174	176	178	180	182	183	438	436	434	432	430	428	426	442	471	155	615	11	7825	
553	73	529	97	528	478	531	168	158	109	520	153	501	512	137	508	499	94	525	123	166	144	93	29	597	7825	
15	611	518	108	98	148	95	458	468	517	106	473	125	114	489	118	127	532	101	503	460	482	533	596	30	7825	
26	600	48	598	6	555	563	61	614	562	44	43	42	53	2	37	535	7	539	40	571	543	587	575	574	7825	
593	33	578	28	620	71	63	565	12	64	582	583	584	573	624	589	91	619	87	586	55	83	39	51	52	7825	
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

142		Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				7825								
8	9	548	57	602	68	4	595	36	47	72	551	534	559	35	66	550	570	5	540	606	601	536	581	45	7825	
618	617	78	569	24	558	622	31	590	579	554	75	92	67	591	560	76	56	621	86	20	25	90	14	612	7825	
552	74	462	513	479	464	467	110	150	105	494	493	141	107	130	470	120	165	465	121	491	115	511	544	82	7825	
80	546	164	113	147	162	159	516	476	521	132	133	485	519	496	156	506	461	161	505	135	126	500	616	10	7825	
557	69	515	111	435	214	172	193	170	200	404	427	430	447	410	431	169	420	173	205	421	486	140	580	46	7825	
54	572	514	112	191	412	454	433	456	426	222	199	196	179	216	195	457	206	453	175	451	472	154	556	70	7825	
567	59	145	481	218	408	301	307	313	319	325	327	299	344	282	267	359	252	374	189	437	459	167	561	65	7825	
19	607	523	103	186	440	318	324	305	306	312	333	293	342	284	264	362	241	385	400	226	146	480	585	41	7825	
81	545	149	477	441	185	310	311	317	323	304	294	332	279	347	367	259	240	386	407	219	131	495	60	566	7825	
547	79	157	469	211	415	322	303	309	315	316	289	337	278	348	368	258	384	242	192	434	522	104	568	58	7825	
594	32	129	497	201	425	314	320	321	302	308	292	334	340	286	263	363	250	376	203	423	498	128	564	62	7825	
84	542	143	483	187	439	290	291	331	328	329	326	296	338	288	262	364	391	235	180	446	124	502	3	623	7825	
27	599	117	509	445	181	336	335	295	298	297	330	300	346	280	371	255	395	231	197	429	102	524	541	85	7825	
538	88	466	160	455	171	349	353	287	283	281	351	285	276	352	372	254	390	236	399	227	100	526	16	610	7825	
21	605	122	504	436	190	277	273	339	343	345	275	341	274	350	271	355	245	381	443	183	152	474	38	588	7825	
23	603	492	134	416	210	270	260	269	370	365	272	369	266	268	373	361	251	375	449	177	463	163	17	609	7825	
577	49	151	475	202	424	356	366	357	256	261	354	257	360	358	265	253	396	230	405	221	99	527	13	613	7825	
1	625	530	96	215	411	380	234	382	383	379	232	387	233	377	238	378	237	229	401	225	510	116	18	608	7825	
549	77	119	507	208	418	246	392	244	243	247	394	239	393	249	388	248	397	389	450	176	484	142	34	592	7825	
537	89	138	488	422	204	228	224	403	414	432	178	182	188	406	184	409	413	417	198	419	487	139	50	576	7825	
604	22	490	136	452	174	398	402	223	212	194	448	444	438	220	442	217	213	209	428	207	471	155	615	11	7825	
553	73	529	97	528	478	531	168	158	109	520	153	501	512	137	508	499	94	525	123	166	144	93	29	597	7825	
15	611	518	108	98	148	95	458	468	517	106	473	125	114	489	118	127	532	101	503	460	482	533	596	30	7825	
26	600	48	598	6	555	563	61	614	562	44	43	42	53	2	37	535	7	539	40	571	543	587	575	574	7825	
593	33	578	28	620	71	63	565	12	64	582	583	584	573	624	589	91	619	87	586	55	83	39	51	52	7825	
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

170		Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA				7825								
8	9	548	57	602	68	4	595	36	47	72	551	534	559	35	66	550	570	5	540	606	601	536	581	45	7825	
618	617	78	569	24	558	622	31	590	579	554	75	92	67	591	560	76	56	621	86	20	25	90	14	612	7825	
552	74	462	513	479	464	467	110	150	105	494	493	141	107	130	470	120	165	465	121	491	115	511	544	82	7825	
80	546	164	113	147	162	159	516	476	521	132	133	485	519	496	156	506	461	161	505	135	126	500	616	10	7825	
557	69	515	111	301	307	313	319	325	300	326	287	339	371	255	230	396	218	408	439	187	486	140	580	46	7825	
54	572	514	112	318	324	305	306	312	293	333	349	277	366	260	384	242	221	405	426	200	472	154	556	70	7825	
567	59	145	481	310	311	317	323	304	296	330	282	344	267	359	378	248	422	204	172	454	459	167	561	65	7825	
19	607	523	103	322	303	309	315	316	337	289	286	340	373	253	380	246	222	404	170	456	146	480	585	41	7825	
81	545	149	477	314	320	321	302	308	335	291	285	341	369	257	237	389	423	203	438	188	131	495	60	566	7825	
547	79	157	469	294	290	329	292	328	331	327	350	276	370	256	231	395	225	401	435	191	522	104	568	58	7825	
594	32	129	497	332	336	297	334	298	299	295	348	278	261	365	379	247	209	417	173	453	498	128	564	62	7825	
84	542	143	483	347	273	345	275	343	280	274	342	338	269	357	382	244	419	207	429	197	124	502	3	623	7825	
27	599	117	509	279	353	281	351	283	346	352	288	284	263	363	236	390	421	205	431	195	102	524	541	85	7825	
538	88	466	160	271	361	372	268	266	270	368	264	367	272	364	375	251	223	403	176	450	100	526	16	610	7825	
21	605	122	504	355	265	254	358	360	356	258	362	259	262	354	383	243	228	398	178	448	152	474	38	588	7825	
23	603	492	134	374	234	232	386	229	377	235	381	376	388	239	233	385	215	411	182	444	463	163	17	609	7825	
577	49	151	475	252	392	394	240	397	249	391	245	250	238	387	241	393	413	213	433	193	99	527	13	613	7825	
1	625	530	96	407	210	208	409	400	212	402	399	211	410	406	206	201	412	202	183	443	510	116	18	608	7825	
549	77	119	507	219	416	418	217	226	414	224	227	415	216	220	420	425	424	214	432	194	484	142	34	592	7825	
537	89	138	488	457	452	192	185	186	445	449	451	199	446	184	189	190	455	447	196	198	487	139	50	576	7825	
604	22	490	136	169	174	434	441	440	181	177	175	427	180	442	437	436	171	179	428	430	471	155	615	11	7825	
553	73	529	97	528	478	531	168	158	109	520	153	501	512	137	508	499	94	525	123	166	144	93	29	597	7825	
15	611	518	108	98	148	95	458	468	517	106	473	125	114	489	118	127	532	101	503	460	482	533	596	30	7825	
26	600	48	598	6	555	563	61	614	562	44	43	42	53	2	37	535	7	539	40	571	543	587	575	574	7825	
593	33	578	28	620	71	63	565	12	64	582	583	584	573	624	589	91	619	87	586	55	83	39	51	52	7825	
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825

191	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/										https://numbers-magic.com/										@IJTANEJA					7825
8	9	548	57	602	68	4	595	36	47	72	551	534	559	35	66	550	570	5	540	606	601	536	581	45	7825			
618	617	78	569	24	558	622	31	590	579	554	75	92	67	591	560	76	56	621	86	20	25	90	14	612	7825			
552	74	314	309	316	325	301	334	292	274	352	272	354	250	376	421	205	194	432	153	473	116	510	544	82	7825			
80	546	315	313	311	324	302	298	328	275	351	363	263	397	229	225	401	190	436	460	166	533	93	616	10	7825			
557	69	310	317	312	304	322	335	291	341	285	369	257	249	377	221	405	451	175	459	167	126	500	580	46	7825			
54	572	306	308	323	307	321	336	290	339	287	266	360	245	381	417	209	199	427	467	159	525	101	556	70	7825			
567	59	320	318	303	305	319	296	330	345	281	262	364	391	235	226	400	189	437	468	158	124	502	561	65	7825			
19	607	289	332	327	326	293	295	329	277	349	267	359	241	385	415	211	444	182	136	490	123	503	585	41	7825			
81	545	337	294	299	300	333	297	331	344	282	270	356	390	236	410	216	200	426	471	155	526	100	60	566	7825			
547	79	347	340	276	280	273	278	343	338	342	268	358	243	383	416	210	188	438	461	165	524	102	568	58	7825			
594	32	279	286	350	346	353	348	283	284	288	368	258	394	232	217	409	456	170	464	162	528	98	564	62	7825			
84	542	366	254	361	357	259	362	255	355	256	365	253	393	233	224	402	448	178	133	493	523	103	3	623	7825			
27	599	260	372	265	269	367	264	371	271	370	373	261	242	384	425	201	197	429	480	146	527	99	541	85	7825			
538	88	247	252	251	386	237	387	248	246	395	244	392	396	388	219	407	196	430	145	481	121	505	16	610	7825			
21	605	379	374	375	240	389	239	378	380	231	382	234	238	230	423	203	183	443	149	477	127	499	38	588	7825			
23	603	222	215	420	414	419	220	422	227	424	213	412	218	223	228	418	441	185	465	161	522	104	17	609	7825			
577	49	404	411	206	212	207	406	204	399	202	413	214	408	403	208	398	449	177	140	486	119	507	13	613	7825			
1	625	431	172	440	171	428	445	433	173	180	174	176	434	442	179	435	439	169	138	488	521	105	18	608	7825			
549	77	195	454	186	455	198	181	193	453	446	452	450	192	184	447	191	457	187	148	478	122	504	34	592	7825			
537	89	144	463	475	147	472	134	141	137	476	143	462	469	142	139	470	135	466	458	474	111	515	50	576	7825			
604	22	482	163	151	479	154	492	485	489	150	483	164	157	484	487	156	491	160	152	168	513	113	615	11	7825			
553	73	494	518	109	501	114	106	110	97	107	509	497	511	95	498	506	495	96	94	508	112	496	29	597	7825			
15	611	132	108	517	125	512	520	516	529	519	117	129	115	531	128	120	131	530	532	118	130	514	596	30	7825			
26	600	48	598	6	555	563	61	614	562	44	43	42	53	2	37	535	7	539	40	571	543	587	575	574	7825			
593	33	578	28	620	71	63	565	12	64	582	583	584	573	624	589	91	619	87	586	55	83	39	51	52	7825			
7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825	7825		

Above there are only three examples. Complete work as **pdf file** can be download from author's site [2].

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